

THE USE OF INTERNET RESOURCES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES
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Abstract. *This article presents advantages and disadvantages of using internet materials and laptops to teach an English language. Until quite lately, Interbased language learning was a relevant topic mostly to those with a special interest in that area. Recently, though the net has become so widespread in educational organization and houses and its uses have increased so dramatically that the majority of English language teachers have make a started the implications of the net for language leaning .*

Keywords: *Internet resources;Teaching English ; Language learning; Language teaching;Internet technologies,multimedia,communicative technology.*

The global computer web internet is a big media library of hyper- media official paper . With the help of effective look timetable, instructors can search out real and related materials are simply, quickly, at any time and from anywhere. At the same time, the quantity of details is so large and the origination of the data is often uncertain, that today a new ability is starting necessary, the ability to assess, analyze, explain such statistics. The internet is becoming one of the most essential and obtainable sources of real and related texts for the process of teaching a foreign language, and thus an effective carrier of this language and the society of the people who speak it. Teachers and students can use this great archive to prepare and complete tasks, strengthen learning and expand understanding in the classroom. The use of a computer and Internet resources in English classes makes it possible to individualize learning as much as possible, make the learning process creative; increases motivation and interest in learning a foreign language and contributes to the effective formation of foreign language speech competence.

Internet resources play an important role in modern education, including the study of foreign languages at the faculty of electrical engineering. Nowadays new information technologies are intensively introduced into all spheres of our life, including the educational process. In this regard we need to develop methods for using computer information technologies in foreign language learning. The use of Internet resources in foreign language lessons is a relevant direction in the methodology that requires new approaches and non-standard solutions. The aim of the study was to investigate the effectiveness of using internet resources in learning foreign languages at the university educational process. More and more language departments, institutes and schools are now using virtual environments to promote and support language learning. The use of a computer and Internet resources in English classes makes it possible to individualize learning as much as possible, make the learning process creative; increases motivation and interest in learning a foreign language and contributes to the effective formation of foreign language speech competence. The article also touches upon the theoretical substantiation of the application of internet resources in the educational context.

Material in electronic format can be very essential processed using computer programs, turning it , exercises can be used in language classes. For project-based forms of learning, the Internet serves as a universal search tool. At the same time, students learn to independently look for the necessary information, systematize the data found, sort them and evaluate them. The Internet acts in this situation as a tool for the development of independence and autonomy of

students. The Internet opens up new perspectives for teachers and learners of a foreign language. Firstly, it becomes possible to easily, quickly and quite cheaply establish contacts with native speakers or foreign language learners from other countries, experts to discuss various topics. Thus, many partnerships between classes from different countries, the so-called E-Mail tandems, are already actively functioning today. More and more educational materials for foreign language learners are offered on the Internet. Teachers need to give students the opportunity to individually expand and deepen their language knowledge.. However, the offer of online language courses (for self-study) is still not enough.

A clear advantage of such exercises is that, along with traditional exercises . In the online format, however, instructors cannot use any marking (underlining, writing), as students often do when completing traditional tasks in a textbook or workbook for a textbook. The advantage of such exercises is also instant feedback (students can immediately after completing the task or in the course of performing individual stages of the exercise receive information about the correctness of their decisions). In case of incorrect answers, a hint appears in the window.

However, interactive exercises distributed over the Internet have a number of advantages over their paper counterparts. First, they provide students with more opportunities to express their individuality than traditional group classes: the time, place, duration, pace of learning can be determined by the students themselves. Independent learning, among other things, can be stimulated by the diagnosis of student achievement (entrance tests, ongoing knowledge control tests) and purposefully organized feedback. Electronic tasks provide "patient" support for students: the same mistakes can be corrected by a computer countless times without losing patience. The computer does not succumb to any mood swings and does not feel "personally affected" if the student makes mistakes. The exercises can be repeated at any time any number of times, even without the involvement of additional materials.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the Internet provides many opportunities to improve the quality of teaching a foreign language and to create incentives for learning. It is an excellent assistant in the organization of the learning process, namely in teaching various types of speech activity, but despite the many obvious advantages of the Internet, many experts who actively use it in their teaching practice and advocate the introduction of new technology in the educational process, emphasize the need for rational, methodologically justified , strictly dosed , proportionally differentiated depending on the aspect and purpose of teaching use of the Internet in the classroom.

The didactic potential of the Internet is very great. It can become a means of achieving educational goals, both for the student and for the teacher. In this case, the teacher becomes an assistant doing the work that is most organic to the modern educational context. The internet does not replace the teacher but becomes one of the most important means of teaching a foreign language in the modern stage.

REFERENCES

1. Rudenko-Morgun O. I. Computer technologies as a new form of education Modern information technologies in education / I. Robert / Shkola-Press / 2004
2. Polilova T.A., Ponomareva V.V. The introduction of computer technology in the teaching of foreign languages. // IYASH. – 2007
3. Khazhgaliyeva.G, Kassymova.A, Medeshov.A The role of internet resources in learning foreign languages at the faculty of electrical engineering/ October 2023

4. E3S Web of Conferences 431(3):02002/P(12-15)